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Cláudia Teixeira is a PhD student in Biology. One of her main passions is molecular biology. Her research mainly focuses on fish nutrition, physiological responses, and molecular and biochemical endpoints assessment. Her main goals are to highlight the importance of small molecules like amino acids, determine nutritional requirements for species of interest, and apply them in aquaculture in the future.

UNDER THE MAGNIFIER: NEW INSIGHTS INTO THE CAATINGA NATIVE BEES

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Abstract

Bees have critical ecosystem roles, being crucial for plant sexual reproduction and enhancing ecosystem diversity. Over 20,000 species of bees, with the vast majority being solitary bees (~ 85%), are known around the globe. The bee species inhabiting the Caatinga biome face challenges in this unique ecosystem, which is characterised by a very dry season followed by an opposite rainy season. Caatinga is also

being subjected to anthropisation, which can significantly impact bee communities. Along with the diverse threats to which bee populations are exposed, there is a lack of knowledge of the species that live in this biome. To fill this gap, the traditional methods of identification, based on taxonomic surveys, may not be enough. This method is complex as there is a lack of suitable taxonomic keys, requiring expertise that is not readily available to obtain. In this sense, molecular barcoding may be a helpful tool in bee identification, which uses a small region from the genome, comparing it to a database to identify the species precisely. Although one technique does not exclude the use of the other, at the moment, the information available for bees in the Caatinga biome is scarce. This work focused on identifying primers that could be used for barcoding, allowing the identification of the diversity of bees. For this purpose, a literature review was conducted to identify new genera and species of bees for the Caatinga biome, increasing its number to 262 different bee species. Afterwards, 68 primer sets were identified and can now be used for barcoding the caatinga species according to the different genera or species. This work contains valuable information for bees inhabiting the Caatinga biome, increasing its monitorisation and the conservation of bee populations.

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